

How to run MSM(PCM)TD-DFT calculations. From “Improving PCM in Protic Media: Markov State Models for TD-DFT calculations”

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Introduction

This tutorial is intended to explain how to run our proposed Markov State Model/Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (MSM(PCM)TD-DFT) protocol from the article “Improving PCM in Protic Media: Markov State Models for TD-DFT calculations”. Thus, this document is mainly focused on operational aspects with brief mentions to the underlying theories, algorithms and software involved. The instructions given here can be followed by using folders that can be accessed on this digital repository. We also make reference to several custom scripts in those folders, which need certain naming conventions to work properly, as pointed out in this tutorial. It is assumed that a Linux operative system is used (here we worked with Ubuntu 24) when referring to the command user interface (CLI). Experienced users may note that there are several ways in which this workflow could be optimized, and one of our future objectives is to provide a cleaner way to perform this process. Here, we considered useful to provide scripts for this first implementation in order to make the MSM(PCM)TD-DFT method available to as many researchers as possible, as soon as possible.

Figure 1 shows all the steps involved in performing our calculations, as discussed on the main manuscript.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the calculations performed in this work. Computational results or “objects” are numbered from i) to viii) and cited throughout this tutorial. Objects obtained from simulations or analysis using AMBER are highlighted in orange, while those obtained from Gaussian appear in purple. Objects obtained from custom python scripts or the python library pyEMMA are shown in blue.

Step i. Optimizing the structures of the photoactive compound and the solvent

The folder 1_RESP contains inputs for Gaussian 16 (.com files). We start from drawings of the photoactive molecule (Benzo[b]fluorenone) and the solvent (Ethanol). Optimizations are run using the commands `pop=MK`, `SCF=tight` and `IOP(6/33=2,6/42=6)` to save RESP charges, needed to create the topology for molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. Outputs (.log files) are then renamed as `BBF.log` and `EOH.log`, respectively, and copied to the next folder (2_BOX). Using three characters acronyms for each molecule makes it easier the handling of future files and scripts.

Step ii. Preparing the topology of the solvent box

The folder 2_BOX is created for this step. We only take the files `BBF.log` and `EOH.log` from 1_RESP. We obtain .mol2 and .frcmod files needed to create the solvent box using antechamber and parmchk2 (from the Amber suite of programs). To that end, we run these instructions in the CLI:

```
Shell
antechamber -i BBF.log -fi gout -o BBF.mol2 -fo mol2 -pf y -c resp -nc 0 -rn BBF
antechamber -i EOH.log -fi gout -o EOH.mol2 -fo mol2 -pf y -c resp -nc 0 -rn EOH
parmchk2 -i BBF.mol2 -f mol2 -o BBF.frcmod
parmchk2 -i EOH.mol2 -f mol2 -o EOH.frcmod
```

A PDB file of each molecule can be generated using tleap (from Amber). We employed the following script, called `leaprc`:

```
leaprc
source leaprc.gaff
BBF = loadmol2 BBF.mol2
loadamberparams BBF.frcmod
check BBF
EOH = loadmol2 EOH.mol2
loadamberparams EOH.frcmod
check EOH
savepdb BBF BBF.pdb
savepdb EOH EOH.pdb
```

The script is run in the CLI as:

```
Shell
tleap leaprc
```

The individual PDBs are then used to generate the a cubic box with BBF at the center, surrounded by ethanol molecules using Packmol [1]. The sides of the box are set to 30 Å with the following `packmol.inp` script:

```

tolerance 2.0
filetype pdb
output BBF_EOH.pdb
structure BBF.pdb
  number 1
  fixed 15. 15. 15. 0. 0. 0.
  centerofmass
end structure
structure EOH.pdb
  number 250
  inside cube 0. 0. 0. 30
end structure

```

packmol.inp

Which is run in the CLI as:

```
packmol < packmol.inp
```

Shell

The command `number 250` indicates the number of ethanol molecules to be added. This value was estimated from the density and molecular weight of ethanol and the volume of the box (in Å) as follows:

$$N = \frac{\delta(g.cm^{-3}).V(\text{Å}^3).10^{-24}(cm^3.\text{Å}^{-3}).N_A(mol^{-1})}{MW(g.mol^{-1})}$$

with δ , V , N_A and MW being the density of the solvent, the volumen of the box, Avogadro's number and the molecular weight of the solvent, respectively. We are now able to obtain the topology and coordinate files that Amber requires to run molecular dynamics simulations. We use the `xleap.inp` script:

```

source leaprc.gaff
BBF = loadmol2 BBF.mol2
loadamberparams BBF.frcmod
check BBF
EOH = loadmol2 EOH.mol2
loadamberparams EOH.frcmod
check EOH
BBF_EOH = loadpdb BBF_EOH.pdb
set BBF_EOH box {30,30,30}
saveamberparm BBF_EOH BBF_EOH.top BBF_EOH.crd
saveoff BBF_EOH BBF_EOH.lib
savepdb BBF_EOH BBF_EOH_xleap.pdb

```

xleap.inp

The command `set BBF_EOH box {x,y,z}` has to coincide with the size of the box set in `packmol.inp`, as is this case. We run the `xleap.inp` script with the command:

```
xleap < xleap.inp
```

Shell

Step iii. Running molecular dynamics simulations

The MD simulations are run in a standard way in `3_Trajectories`. We take the files `BBF_EOH.top` and `BBF_EOH.crd` from `2_BOX` and paste them in four identical subfolders (`01`, `02`, `03`, `04`, which we will refer to as `{01..04}`, in reference to a command we will use later). The MSM protocol enables the processing of independent simulations together, which in turns mean that the work of computing trajectories can be divided and parallelized. Within the folders `3_Trajectories/{01..04}`, we also paste `BBF_EOH.crd` as `ref.crd`, because it is required on the first Amber computation. The center of this step is the `RunScripts.sh` file, which contains the instructions for the many steps required to obtain MD simulations, including minimizations, heating under constant volume and the trajectory simulation under constant pressure and temperature. `RunScripts.sh` assumes the use of CUDA for each step, but the file can be edited to change the device in which the computation is run or call other platforms [2].

```
RunScripts.sh
export CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES=0
pmemd.cuda -O -i min.in -o min.out -p BBF_EOH.top -c BBF_EOH.crd -r min.rst \
           -ref ref.crd
sleep 5
pmemd.cuda -O -i min2.in -o min2.out -p BBF_EOH.top -c min.rst -r min2.rst
sleep 5
pmemd.cuda -O -i ntva.in -o ntva.out -p BBF_EOH.top -c min2.rst -r ntva.rst \
           -x ntva.mdcrd -inf ntva.mdinfo -ref min2.rst
sleep 5
pmemd.cuda -O -AllowSmallBox -i md.in -o md.out -p BBF_EOH.top -c ntva.rst \
           -r md.rst -x md.mdcrd -inf md.mdinfo -ref ntva.rst
sleep 5
```

The scripts `min.in`, `min2.in`, `ntva.in` and `md.in`, referenced in `RunScripts.sh`, correspond to the inputs for each step, in which computation details are set as follows:

```
min.in
Minimization with Cartesian restraints for the solute
&cntrl
imin=1,      ! Run minimization instead of MD
maxcyc=200, ! Maximum number of minimization cycles
ntpr=5,      ! Print energy information every 5 step
ntr=1,       ! Apply positional restraints
&end
Group input for restrained atoms
100.0
RES 1
END
END
```

```
min2.in
Minimization with Cartesian restraints for the entire molecular system
&cntrl
imin=1,      ! Run minimization instead of MD
maxcyc=300, ! Maximum number of minimization cycles
ntpr=5,      ! Print energy information every 5 steps
&end
```

Heating up the system - Equilibration Stage

ntva.in

```
&cntrl
  nstlim=25000, dt=0.002,      ! 25000 steps, time step of 2 fs (total 50 ps)
  ntx=1,  irest=0,            ! Read initial coordinates and restart
  ntr=500,                    ! Print energy info every 500 steps
  ntwr=2000,                  ! Write restart file every 2000 steps
  ntwx=2000,                  ! Write trajectory coordinates every 2000 steps
  tempi=10.0, temp0=300.0,    ! Start at 10 K and heat up to 300 K
  ntt=3, gamma_ln= 30.0,    ! Langevin thermostat, collision freq. in ps-1
  ig=-1,                      ! Random seed for Langevin dynamics
  ntb=1, ntp=0,              ! Constant volume simulation (no pressure control)
  ntc=2,                      ! SHAKE constraints on hydrogen bonds
  ntf=2,                      ! Force field hydrogen treatment
  ioutfm=1                    ! Write output files in NetCDF format
&end
```

In the md.in file, one crucial command is ntwx, which indicates the frequency in which the coordinates of the system are recorded. The features to be analyzed for MSM depend only on these coordinates. That means the command ntwx fixes the lag time between two consecutive frames to be analyzed (1 ps in this example).

Constant Pressure, Constant Temperature Equilibration

md.in

```
&cntrl
  nstlim=100000000,          ! 100,000,000 steps
  dt=0.001,                  ! 1 fs time step (100 ns total)
  ntx=5,  irest=1,          ! Read coordinates and velocities
  irest=1,                   ! Continue from previous run
  ntr=1000,                  ! Print energy info every 1000 steps (1 ps)
  ntwr=1000,                 ! Write restart file every 1000 steps (1 ps)
  ntwx=1000,                 ! Write coordinates every 1000 steps (1ps)
  temp0=300.0, ntt=3,       ! Langevin thermostat (ntt=3)
  gamma_ln=30.0,            ! Collision frequency in ps-1
  barostat=2,               ! Monte Carlo-like Berendsen barostat
  ig=-1,                    ! Random seed for Langevin dynamics
  ntb=2,                    ! Constant pressure periodic boundary conditions
  ntp=1,                    ! Isotropic pressure coupling
  ntc=2,                    ! SHAKE constraints on hydrogen bonds
  ntf=2,                    ! Force field hydrogen treatment
  cut=10.0,                 ! Nonbonded interaction cutoff distance (10 Å)
  tol=0.0000001,           ! SHAKE tolerance for constrained bonds
  ioutfm=1                  ! Write output files in NetCDF format
&end
Ewald summation parameters for long-range electrostatics
&ewald
  skinnb=1,                  ! Buffer size for nonbonded neighbor list
&end
```

RunScripts.sh is typically run with the following command (after setting the executable bit with chmod +x), though implementations may vary:

```
nohup ./RunScripts.sh &
```

Shell

However, this has to be repeated once on each {01..04} folder. A quicker way to do this is

running, in `3_Trajectories` (the parent folder of `{01..04}`) the following for loop command:

```
for dir in {01..04}; do cd ${dir}; nohup ./RunScripts.sh & cd ..;done
```

Shell

As indicated in `RunScripts.sh`, the output on each `{01..04}` folder is saved as `md.mdcrd`, which are skipped on our file structure to save space. These `md.mdcrd` files should be copied, in our folder structure, to `4_Features/{01..04}`, after converting them to `.nc` (netCDF) files. This is done with the following `cpptraj`¹ script:

```
parm BBF_EOH.top
trajin md.mdcrd
autoimage
trajout md.nc netcdf
run
```

`cpptraj_netcdf.in`

We can run this script on each of the `{01..04}` subfolders simultaneously by using the following command on `3_Trajectories`:

```
for dir in {01..04}; do cd ${dir}; cpptraj -i cpptraj_netcdf.in -o /dev/null & \
cd ..; done
```

Shell

With all this, we have one trajectory file, `md.nc`, on each of the subfolders `{01..04}`. We move them to `4_Features/{01..04}` and continue with the next step.

¹An AmberTools program.

Step iv. Extracting features from trajectories

This step is key in the sense that features are the main input for fitting a MSM. As discussed in the manuscript, we focus on distances and angles associated to H-bonds. It can be inferred from this tutorial how other distances or angles can also be extracted. We discussed in the main manuscript that these other features can be evaluated by their influence on the independent components (see the following section). In `4_Features/{01..04}` we have the `md.nc` files, and we need to also paste the topology `BBF_EOH.top` files, because it is required by `cpptraj`.

The system `BBF_EOH` has only one kind of relevant distance, between the O1 atom in `BBF` and H6 in `EtOH`. However, this system has 250 `EtOH` molecules, which means the first step is to extract 250 `BBF@O1 - EOH@H6`² (d_{OH}) distances on each frame. There are also two types of angles we may be interested in, which are used in the manuscript: i) `BBF@C13 - BBF@O1 - EOH@H6` (a_{COH}) and ii) `BBF@O1 - EOH@H6 - BBF@O1` (a_{OHO}). Dihedral angles can also be extracted, but we found they are not relevant in the time-lagged independent component analysis (TICA). The extraction of distances and angles is done with the following script:

```
cpptraj_feat.in
parm BBF_EOH.top
trajin md.nc
for residues RES inmask :EOH
  distance oh6$RES :1@O1 $RES@H6 out dist-o01h06res.dat
  angle coh$RES :1@C13 :1@O1 $RES@H6 out ang-c13o01h06res.dat
  angle oho$RES :1@O1 $RES@H6 $RES@O1 out ang-o01h06reso01res.dat
done
```

which is run repeatedly with the command:

```
Shell
for dir in {01..04}; do cd ${dir}; cpptraj -i cpptraj_feat.in -o /dev/null & \
cd ..; done
```

This lead us to have the set of files [`dist-o01h06res.dat`, `ang-c13o01h06res.dat`, `ang-o01h06reso01res.dat`] on `4_Features/{01..04}`, in which 250 distances and angles are listed for each frame saved in each simulation. We saved these files as a `to_filter.zip` file on each folder. We need to do two main actions on the rows of these files:

1. First, on `dist-o01h06res.dat`, we need determine which of the 250 distances are the shortest ones. We need to record both the distance values and the indices assigned to the closest `EtOH` molecules on each frame.
2. Then, knowing the closest `EtOH` molecule's indices for every frame, we select the corresponding angles in `ang-c13o01h06res.dat` and `ang-o01h06reso01res.dat`. That way, we will have for each frame of each trajectory the shortest d_{OH} distances and their corresponding a_{COH} and a_{OHO} angles.

This can be achieved with our custom `feature_filter.py` script, which reduces the 250 d_{OH} , a_{COH} and a_{OHO} features on every frame to just 5³. This script assumes the `.dat` files have been moved to a `to_filter` subfolder, for an easier handling of the files in the original folder structure (in which the files of the preceding step are also present). If we have `feature_filter.py` on the parent folder `4_Features` we can paste it⁴ on each subfolder and move the `.dat` files to a new `to_filter` subfolder with the command:

²Here we use the naming convention of Amber.

³This can be edited on line 31 of the script.

⁴A better approach is creating an alias for the script to avoid duplicating it.

Shell

```
for dir in {01..04}; do cp feature_filter.py ${dir}; cd ${dir}; \
  mkdir to_filter; mv *.dat to_filter/; cd ..; done
```

`feature_filter.py` only requires basic Python libraries and can be run with the following command, from the parent folder `4_Features`:

Shell

```
for dir in {01..04}; do cd ${dir}; python3 feature_filter.py & cd ..; done
```

The outputs are saved by the script on the folder `4_Features/outputs` as `data_01.csv`, `data_02.csv`, etc. In our file structure, those files have been moved to `5-7_MSM/01_data`. It is important to note that the script will work only if the naming convention from `cpptraj_feat.in` is used, that is:

1. Distance files begin with “dist-”, while angles files begin with “ang-”.
2. `.dat` filenames present the same atom order and labels between “dist-” and “ang-” files. We opted for adding the suffix “res” to indicate solvent atoms (in reference to the RES name used in the `cpptraj` loop) to easily recognize within the filenames which atoms correspond to the solvent and which to the photoactive compound.

From the first convention, the python script is able to differentiate distances files, which are needed in the step in which the shortest H-bond distances are found on every frame. The second convention is needed to associate each angle file to its corresponding distance file (in case several distances and angles are used as input). This is done in the in the clause: “if distance_name in angle_name:” in line 38 of `feature_filter.py`. We can see, by comparing the filenames `dist-o01h06res.dat` and `ang-c13o01h06res.dat`, that the string `o01h06res` from the distance filename is present in the angle filename. This links these files together in the `feature_filter.py` script. Without this linking the script wouldn’t be able to use the solvent indices from the shortest H-bonds on every frame to select the corresponding bond angles.

It is relevant to note that the `data_XX.csv` files contain, on the first row, the naming of each individual feature, with the following conventions:

1. Features are ordered alphabetically, which makes angles appear before distances.
2. Angle column names have four parts: the “ang_” string; the distance name corresponding to that angle; the angle name; an order number, going from 1 to 5, in which 1 corresponds to the shortest distance and 5 the fifth shortest. Thus “ang_o01h06res_c13o01h06res_1” reads: “the angle, associated to the (shortest) bond between `o01` and `h06res`, involving `c13`, `o01` and `h06res`”
3. Distance column names have, in turn, three parts: the “dist_” string; the distance name; an order number, going from 1 to 5, in which 1 corresponds to the shortest distance and 5 the fifth shortest.

Step v. Time-lagged independent component analysis (TICA)

Steps v. to vii. are necessarily done in the same folder, which we call 5-7_MSM. We start from the four `data_XX.csv` files which we copy to the subfolder `01_data`. The analysis is done in a python notebook, `02_MSM.ipynb`. This requires to create a miniconda environment, to install a specific python version with the corresponding libraries, which also need specific versions to be compatible with pyEMMA. The following commands are run to install miniconda:

```
Shell
mkdir -p ~/miniconda3
wget https://repo.anaconda.com/miniconda/Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh -O \
~/miniconda3/miniconda.sh
bash ~/miniconda3/miniconda.sh -b -u -p ~/miniconda3
rm ~/miniconda3/miniconda.sh
```

We then initialize miniconda:

```
Shell
unset PYTHONPATH
source ~/miniconda3/bin/activate
```

In miniconda, we create a new environment, and install Python 3.9 and the required libraries on it:

```
Shell
conda create -n pyemma39 -c conda-forge python=3.9
conda activate pyemma39
conda install -c conda-forge pyemma=2.5.7
conda install -c conda-forge numpy=1.19
conda install -c conda-forge libtiff=4.3.0
conda install -c conda-forge pandas=1.3
conda install -c conda-forge mdshare
conda install -c conda-forge MDAnalysis
conda install -c conda-forge nglview=2.7.7
conda install -c conda-forge ipywidgets=7.7.2
conda install jupyterlab=2
```

Once this is done, the `pyemma39` environment can be selected on the integrated development environment (IDE) of choice, like Visual Studio Code or Positron (the latter being the one we mostly used). We open the `02_MSM.ipynb` file, which starts by loading the relevant libraries:

```
02_MSM.ipynb
%matplotlib inline
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import pyemma
import glob
import string
import os
from datetime import datetime
from collections import defaultdict
import re
```

Then, we make the script obtain the data filenames and we indicate the lagtime between rows of the `data_XX.csv` files (1 ps, in this case, see Step iii). We tag some lines with the phrase “SET ACCORDINGLY” to emphasize that those lines can be edited, while the rest does not need to be changed, in general.

02_MSM.ipynb

```
pattern_data = "01_data/data*.csv" #SET ACCORDINGLY
data_files = sorted(glob.glob(pattern_data))
step_time_ps = 1 #SET ACCORDINGLY
```

After that, we need to indicate which columns are relevant to be loaded. This should be edited once we realize some features are not needed. For example, if we have added many other features to the `data_XX.csv` files, we will need to test some of them, see which ones influence TICA and then select only those that have significant effects. In this example, we saved on the `data_XX.csv` files 5 distances and 10 angles (5 COH and 5 OHO angles). Because we know that we only need the shortest H-bond and the corresponding angles, we can select only those three features by indicating the column indices 0, 5 and 10.

02_MSM.ipynb

```
data_files_columns = pd.read_csv(data_files[0]).columns
selected_columns = list(data_files_columns)
selected_columns_indices = [0,5,10] #SET ACCORDINGLY
selected_columns = [selected_columns[i] for i in selected_columns_indices]
```

Now we can load the data:

02_MSM.ipynb

```
data = [np.loadtxt(f, delimiter=',', skiprows=1, usecols=selected_columns_indices) for f in data_files]
data_concatenate = np.concatenate(data)
data_pyemma = pyemma.coordinates.load(data_files)
```

At this point it is relevant to inspect the data by plotting histograms of the three features we are using to describe the BBF-EtOH system (Figure 2). It is worth noting for prospective users that labels may be further edited using vector graphics editors if the command `plt.savefig("NAME.svg", format="svg")` is included to export a vector image.

02_MSM.ipynb

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1, figsize=(5,4))
pyemma.plots.plot_feature_histograms(data_concatenate, feature_labels=selected_columns, ax=ax)
```


Figure 2: Histograms corresponding to the three selected features.

It is important to remember that TICA is sensible to features with high autocorrelation. For that reason, one of the characteristics that serves as an easy way to know whether a feature is useful to describe the system for our purposes is the bimodality. We can see that the H-bond distance (`dist-o01h06res_1`) histogram has two peaks, which suggest that at times there is a H-bond present and at other times the closest EOH@H6 atom is too far away. Something

similar is detected when inspecting the OHO angle histogram, while the COH angle shows it less clearly. Bimodality is indicative, in this case, of the existence of metastable states, which are visited during a certain period of time before the system “jumps” to another metastable state. If this is the case, the autocorrelation will be detected when running TICA, which is done with the commands:

```
tica_dimension = 2 #SET ACCORDNGLY
tica = pyemma.coordinates.tica(data, lag=10,dim=tica_dimension) #SET ACCORDNGLY
tica_output = tica.get_output()
tica_concatenated = np.concatenate(tica_output)
```

02_MSM.ipynb

Two variables are relevant here: the number of independent components and the lagtime (that is, how many frames are skipped before computing the autocorrelation, which is different from the frame lagtime). The pyEMMA tutorial [3] discusses how to tune these variables. We may see if our analysis is promising by inspecting the time evolution of the independent components.

```
fig, axes = plt.subplots(tica_dimension, 1, figsize=(12, 5), sharex=True)
x = 0.001* step_time_ps * np.arange(tica_output[0].shape[0])
for i, (ax, tic) in enumerate(zip(axes.flat, tica_output[0].T)): # Here we select only one run
    ax.plot(x, tic)
    ax.set_ylabel('TICA {}'.format(i + 1))
axes[-1].set_xlabel('time / ns')
fig.tight_layout()
```

02_MSM.ipynb

Figure 3: Time evolution of the two ICs fitted with TICA.

We can also evaluate how the two ICs are correlated with the features we selected.

```
new_labels = ["COH angle", "OHO angle", "OH distance"]

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(8, 5))
i = ax.imshow(tica.feature_TIC_correlation.T, cmap='bwr', vmin=-1, vmax=1)

ax.set_xticks(range(len(selected_columns)))
ax.set_xticklabels(new_labels, rotation=45)
ax.set_xlabel('input feature')
ax.set_yticks(range(tica_output[0].shape[1]))
ax.set_yticklabels(list(range(1, tica_output[0].shape[1] + 1)))
ax.set_ylabel('TICA')
cbar = fig.colorbar(i, orientation="horizontal", pad=0.3, aspect=40)
cbar.ax.set_xlabel("Correlation")

plt.show()
```

02_MSM.ipynb

We can see in Figure 4 that the H-bond distance and the OHO angle highly correlate with TICA-1, while the COH angle has a slight influence in both TICA-1 and TICA-2. More

Figure 4: Correlations between the independent components and the input features.

importantly, we can see that there is no correlation between the OH distance and the OHO angle with TICA-2. In order to capture the main features that describe the equilibrium dynamics of our systems, several features could be tested, and then those without correlation on the ICs are discarded, as we mentioned before. In the main article this kind of observation was used to reduce the number of input features,

We can also create plots with histograms of our independent components and contour plots of the TICA space, which in this case show two distinguishable regions.

```

02_MSM.ipynb
fig, axes = plt.subplots(1, 3, figsize=(15, 4))
pyemma.plots.plot_feature_histograms(tica_concatenated, feature_labels=['TICA$_1$', 'TICA$_2$'], ax=axes[0])
for i, dim in enumerate(['y', 'x']):
    axes[0].plot(tica_concatenated[:30000, 1 - i], np.linspace(-0.2 + i, 0.8 + i, 30000), color='C2', alpha=0.6)
    axes[0].annotate(
        '${}(time)'.format(dim),
        xy=(3, 0.6 + i),
        xytext=(3, i),
        arrowprops=dict(fc='C2', ec='None', alpha=0.6, width=2))
pyemma.plots.plot_density(*tica_concatenated.T, ax=axes[1])
pyemma.plots.plot_free_energy(*tica_concatenated.T, ax=axes[2])
axes[1].set_xlabel('TICA$_1$')
axes[1].set_ylabel('TICA$_2$')
axes[2].set_xlabel('TICA$_1$')
axes[2].set_ylabel('TICA$_2$')
fig.tight_layout()

```


Figure 5: Histograms with TICA evolution (left), density contour plot (middle) and free energy contour plot (right) of the time-lagged independent components.

Step vi. Clustering of the TICA space to define microstates.

A continuous space is not suitable to fit a Markov State Model. For that reason, we need to use a clustering algorithm to divide the space into discrete sections. In the following code, the number of cluster centers (k) is set to 100, but can be edited.

```
cluster = pyemma.coordinates.cluster_kmeans(tica_concatenated, k=100, max_iter=200) #SET ACCORDINGLY
```

We can now inspect how the cluster centers have been distributed.

```
fig, axes = plt.subplots(1,2 , figsize=(10, 4))
pyemma.plots.plot_feature_histograms(
    tica_concatenated, ['TICA {}'.format(i + 1) for i in range(tica.dimension())], ax=axes[0])
for ax, (i, j) in zip(axes.flat[1:], [[0, 1]]):
    pyemma.plots.plot_density(*tica_concatenated[:, [i, j]].T, ax=ax, cbar=False, alpha=0.1)
    ax.scatter(*cluster.clustercenters[:, [i, j]].T, s=15, c='C1')
    ax.set_xlabel('TICA {}'.format(i + 1))
    ax.set_ylabel('TICA {}'.format(j + 1))
fig.tight_layout()
```


Figure 6: Histogram (left) of the TICA values and positions of the cluster centers on the TICA space (right).

The area surrounding each cluster is called a microstate in this context, and its definition enable us to fit a MSM.

Step vii. Fitting a MSM.

A key parameter must be selected in this step: the lagtime (not to be confused with the lagtime as time between frames, or the parameter used for computing autocorrelation in TICA). This lagtime is used to create a transition matrix between the 100 sections in which we divided the TICA space. This matrix answer the question: in average, what is the probability for the system of being in a microstate j at time equal τ (the lagtime) if at time equal to zero it is located at a microstate i ? The fitted transition probability matrix changes when different τ values are evaluated. For that reason, we need to compare matrices to make the final selection of τ .

Each reversible transition matrix which has many eigenvectors and eigenvalues associated to it. In MSM, the first eigenvector correspond to the equilibrium distribution, in terms of the microstates we found earlier, and its corresponding eigenvalue is equal to one. The other eigenvectors are related to slow processes and, as mentioned in the manuscript, their eigenvalues (λ_i) are related to the corresponding timescale (t_i) as:

$$t_i = -\frac{\tau}{\ln |\lambda_i|}$$

Each eigenvalue, and thus each timescale, is dependent on the value of τ selected to fit the MSM, up to a point in which it converges. MSM can only solve for processes that converges at τ values smallest than the corresponding timescale. As we will see, this also is evident by inspecting the eigenvectors. Thus, the first step on fitting a MSM is, in reality, fitting many MSM by progressively changing the τ parameter and plotting how the timescales change with every lagtime.

```
its = pyemma.msm.its(cluster.dtrajs,
lags=[10,50,100,200,400,600,800,1000], nits=2, errors='bayes') #SET ACCORDINGLY
pyemma.plots.plot_implied_timescales(its, ylog=False);
```

02_MSM.ipynb

In the previous code, we can set both the lagtimes (in terms of the number of frames we skip to compute the transition probability matrix) and the number of implied timescales we want to display. While we set `nits=1` for the analysis on the main manuscript, here we show what happens when a process do not converge, as seen in the following Figure.

Figure 7: Evolution of the implied timescales as a function of the lagtime.

We can see that the slowest process converges at around 600 steps (i.e. 600 ps), while the

second process do not converge. We can extract the exact value for this implied timescale (in step units), together with the confidence interval, by using the following commands, in which the lag time (600) and the process index (0, as it is the first) need to be indicated.

```
selected_lagtime = 600 #SET ACCORDINGLY
lagtime_index = list(its.lagtimes).index(selected_lagtime)
lo, hi = its.get_sample_conf(conf=0.95, process=0) #SET PROCESS ACCORDINGLY
print(its.timescales[lagtime_index][0]) #SET PROCESS ACCORDINGLY
print(lo[lagtime_index], hi[lagtime_index])
```

02_MSM.ipynb

The file 02_MSM.ipynb also shows how to edit the previous plot to include the timescales in ps, by using the parameter `step_time_ps` we defined at the beginning, that we skip here. We can finally set the lagtime to 600 for the MSM.

```
msm = pyemma.msm.estimate_markov_model(cluster.dtrajs, lag=600) #SET ACCORDINGLY
dtrajs_concatenated = np.concatenate(cluster.dtrajs)
```

02_MSM.ipynb

We can then visualize the equilibrium distribution in terms of our microstates.

```
fig, ax, misc = pyemma.plots.plot_contour(
    *tica_concatenated.T, msm.pi[dtrajs_concatenated],
    cbar_label='stationary_distribution',
    method='nearest', mask=True)
#ax.scatter(*cluster.clustercenters[:, [0, 1]].T, s=15, c='C1')
ax.set_xlabel('TICA$_1$')
ax.set_ylabel('TICA$_2$')
fig.tight_layout()
```

02_MSM.ipynb

Figure 8: Equilibrium distribution found from MSM.

By uncommenting the fifth line, the position of each cluster center can also be displayed. It can be instructive to compare this plot with the equilibrium distribution, as it is then done in 02_MSM.ipynb and shown in the supporting information of the main manuscript. We may also want to check whether the first eigenvalue is in fact equal to one.

```
eigvec = msm.eigenvectors_right()
print('first eigenvector is one: {}'.format(
    np.allclose(eigvec[:, 0], 1, atol=1e-15), eigvec[:, 0].min(), eigvec[:, 0].max()))
```

02_MSM.ipynb

We get a “True” value as output, confirming this condition. Now we can continue by inspecting the second and third eigenvectors, which are key to understand the kind of process that the MSM had solved.

```
fig, axes = plt.subplots(1,2, figsize=(12, 6)) #SET THE NUMBER OF PLOTS ACCORDINGLY
for i, ax in enumerate(axes.flat):
    pyemma.plots.plot_contour(
        *tica_concatenated[:, :2].T,
        eigvec[dtrajs_concatenated, i + 1],
        ax=ax, cmap='PiYG',
        cbar_label='{}. right eigenvector'.format(i + 2), mask=True)
    #ax.scatter(*cluster.clustercenters.T, s=15, c='C1')
    ax.set_xlabel('TICA 1')
    ax.set_ylabel('TICA 2')
fig.tight_layout()
```

02_MSM.ipynb

Figure 9: Second (left) and third (right) eigenvectors of the fitted MSM.

Figure 9 shows some regions in magenta and others in green, indicating regions which the system leaves and those to which it arrives (respectively) in any of the two slow processes. It is noteworthy that the inverse process is characterized by the same timescale. We can clearly see that the second eigenvector is associated to a process involving two well defined regions. These regions are mainly delimited by the value of TICA-1, which is in turn strongly associated to the H-bond distance. As Figure 4 shows a positive correlation between TICA-1 and the OH distance, we infer that higher TICA-1 values are linked to bigger distances. This also indicates that the region to the left corresponds to the situation in which a BBF molecule is bonded to an EtOH, while the region to the right is associated with an absence of such bond. We can further corroborate this by inspecting specifics frames belonging to each group, as we will see further on.

On the other side, the plot of the third eigenvector does not seem to be associated with an physically interpretable process. This, together with the fact that the third eigenvalue did not converge, indicates that this MSM can only solve one slow process.

We now may wish to validate the MSM, using the Chapman-Kolmogorov (CK) test. To do this, we need to indicate the number of macrostates, that is, the number of microstates groups that we associate to different chemical arrangements. From the previous discussion, we will set this value (in `msm.cktest()`) to 2.

```
pyemma.plots.plot_cktest(msm.cktest(2)); #SET THE NUMBER OF MACROSTATES ACCORDINGLY
```


Figure 10: Chapman-Kolmogorov test for the fitted MSM. See main text.

The CK test compares the probability that a system in one macrostate jumps to the other (or remains in the same macrostate) from the transition probability matrix (dashed blue lines in Figure 10) to what is effectively observed in our trajectories (continuous black line). Although it can be further improved, we see a good correspondence between these two curves, thus validating the MSM we have fitted.

We can print the equilibrium populations of each macrostate, according to our MSM, as seen in Figure 10. We get that the population of the macrostate 1 is 0.19 and that of macrostate 2 is 0.81.

```
for i, s in enumerate(msm.metastable_sets):
    print('pi_{} = {}'.format(i + 1, msm.pi[s].sum()))
```

Confidence intervals for the macrostate populations can be obtained using a Bayesian Markov model. The command `pyemma.msm.bayesian_markov_model` gives several transition matrices (set with `n_sample`). After identifying the populations of each macrostate (using `bmsm.pcca(2)`) for each transition matrix, statistical uncertainties can be computed.

```

bmsm = pyemma.msm.bayesian_markov_model(cluster.dtrajs, lag=600, nsamples=1000) #SET LAG ACCORDINGLY
bmsm.pcca(2) #SET THE NUMBER OF MACROSTATES ACCORDINGLY

all_pops = np.array([
    [sample.pi[s].sum() for s in bmsm.metastable_sets]
    for sample in bmsm.samples
])

mean = all_pops.mean(axis=0)
std = all_pops.std(axis=0)
lower = np.percentile(all_pops, 2.5, axis=0)
upper = np.percentile(all_pops, 97.5, axis=0)

for i in range(len(bmsm.metastable_sets)):
    print(f'pi_{i+1} = {mean[i]:.4f} ± {std[i]:.4f} 95% CI: [{lower[i]:.4f}, {upper[i]:.4f}]')

```

Although we could infer by comparing Figure 10 with Figure 8 that the macrostate 1 corresponds to the region to the right and that macrostate 2 corresponds to that on the left, we can inspect how the limits between the regions are computed. One such approach is using the Peron cluster cluster analysis (PCCA++), which computes the probability that any microstates belong to a particular macrostate.

```

nstates = 2 #SET THE NUMBER OF MACROSTATES ACCORDINGLY
msm.pcca(nstates)

```

We can then plot the result of this computation.

```

fig, axes = plt.subplots(1, nstates, figsize=(12, 4))
for i, ax in enumerate(axes.flat):
    pyemma.plots.plot_contour(
        *tica_concatenated[:, :2].T,
        msm.metastable_distributions[i][dtrajs_concatenated],
        ax=ax,
        cmap='afmhot_r',
        mask=True,
        cbar_label='metastable distribution {}'.format(i + 1))
    ax.scatter(*cluster.clustercenters[:, [0, 1]].T, s=5, c='k')
    ax.set_xlabel('TICA$_1$')
axes[0].set_ylabel('TICA$_2$')
fig.tight_layout()

```


Figure 11: Memberships of each microstate to each of the two identified macrostates.

From the previous values, we can associate each frame on our trajectories to any of the two macrostates by computing to which macrostate it is more likely to belong. For clarity, we use a strided trajectory (in which the four simulations are concatenated).

```

stride = 10
metastable_trajs_strided = [msm.metastable_assignments[dtrj[::stride]] for dtrj in cluster.dtrajs]
tica_output_strided = [i[::stride] for i in tica_output]
_, _, misc = pyemma.plots.plot_state_map(*np.concatenate(tica_output_strided).T,
                                         np.concatenate(metastable_trajs_strided));
misc['cbar'].set_ticklabels(range(1, nstates + 1))

```

02_MSM.ipynb

Figure 12: Memberships of each microstate to each of the two identified macrostates.

We then confirm that the groups on the right and the left have been labeled as macrostate 1 and 2, respectively, and that the limits of these groups closely match what we saw in Figure 9.

To end this step, and the use of the file 02_MSM.ipynb, we save the results of our computations in the file 03_MSMenv.dill

```
import dill, os, tempfile, shutil

def save_vars(filename):
    to_save = {}
    for k, v in globals().items():
        try:
            dill.dumps(v)
            to_save[k] = v
        except:
            pass

    # atomic write
    fd, tmp = tempfile.mkstemp()
    os.close(fd)
    with open(tmp, "wb") as f:
        dill.dump(to_save, f)
    shutil.move(tmp, filename)

save_vars("03_MSMenu.dill")
```

Step viii. Computation of excitation energies.

To have a prediction of the excitation energies of the two metastable macrostates we have detected by the MSM analysis we need to do the following:

1. Select one point on the TICA space for each of the two macrostates.
2. Find a certain number of frames (here ten) which are the nearest to each point.
3. Export the coordinates of the relevant molecules for each of the $10 \times 2 = 20$ frames.
4. Create and run Gaussian inputs from these 20 sets of coordinates.
5. Process the results of the 20 Gaussian outputs.

We move to the folder 8_TDDFT, carrying the last file we exported, 03_MSMe`nv`.dill, that we rename to 01_MSMe`nv`.dill. We then perform steps 1 to 3 on a new python notebook 02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb, named after the fact that the main function of this script is to generate cpptraj inputs with which the coordinates will be recovered from the original md.nc files (it must be remembered that the input files we used for MSM only contain OHO and COH angles and OH distances, not the full coordinate description of the system). Thus, we begin by loading a similar set of libraries than before, using the same environment that we employed for 02_MSM.ipynb:

```
%matplotlib inline
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import pyemma
import glob
import string
import os
from datetime import datetime
from collections import defaultdict
import re
from warnings import warn as _warn
```

02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb

Now we can load the results from the previous three steps, and begin the final step.

```
import dill

def load_vars(filename):
    with open(filename, "rb") as f:
        data = dill.load(f)
        globals().update(data)

load_vars("01_MSMenv.dill")
```

02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb

1. Select one point on the TICA space for each of the two macrostates.

This could be somewhat trivial if we just plot the free energy landscape of our TICA space and select two points that *we see* have the lowest free energy on each macro state. We have plotted this before (Figure 13):

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(6, 5))
pyemma.plots.plot_free_energy(*tica_concatenated.T, ax=ax)
ax.set_xlabel('TICA$_1$')
ax.set_ylabel('TICA$_2$')
fig.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb

At first glance, we could be tempted to identify macrostate 1 (the one to the right) with a point in the vicinity of (2 , 0) and macrostate 2 (the one to the left) with a point at (-0.5 , -0.2),

Figure 13: Free energy contour plot of the time-lagged independent component space.

but we could try to use a systemic approach. We do this by taking advantage of the functions defined in the pyEMMA library, with slight modifications. For the sake of brevity we refer to section # 0.3 Definitions in 02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb to see the definitions, but we will explain each function in due course.

In our script, we begin by listing to which macrostate every single frame from the four trajectories belongs to:

```

stride = 1 # SET TO ONE FOR THIS SCRIPT
metastable_trajs_strided = [msm.metastable_assignments[dtrj[::stride]] for dtrj in cluster.dtrajs]
tica_output_strided = [i[::stride] for i in tica_output]
_, _, misc = pyemma.plots.plot_state_map(*np.concatenate(tica_output_strided).T,
                                         np.concatenate(metastable_trajs_strided));
misc['cbar'].set_ticklabels(range(1, nstates + 1))

```

02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb

We save that information in the `metastable_trajs_strided` variable. Aside, we list the TICA values of each frame in the variable `tica_output_strided`. Now we need to variables, one for each macrostate, in which only the frames belonging to each one are listed, with their corresponding TICA values.

```

global_state_traj = np.concatenate(metastable_trajs_strided)
tica_data_concatenated = np.concatenate(tica_output_strided).T
state_strided_data_dict = {'state': global_state_traj,
                           'tica_1': tica_data_concatenated[0], 'tica_2': tica_data_concatenated[1]}
state_strided_data_df = pd.DataFrame(data=state_strided_data_dict)
state_strided_data_df_only_tica = state_strided_data_df[['tica_1', 'tica_2']]
state_strided_data_df_state1 = state_strided_data_df[state_strided_data_df['state'] == 0].copy()
state_strided_data_df_state1_only_tica = state_strided_data_df_state1[['tica_1', 'tica_2']]
state_strided_data_df_state2 = state_strided_data_df[state_strided_data_df['state'] == 1].copy()
state_strided_data_df_state2_only_tica = state_strided_data_df_state2[['tica_1', 'tica_2']]

```

02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb

Now, for each macrostate we look for the coordinates of the point with lowest free energy using the same functions pyEMMA employs to display the free energy plot. That is, `imported_get_histogram` and `imported_to_free_energy`.

```

tica1_state1 = state_strided_data_df_state1_only_tica['tica_1'].tolist()
tica2_state1 = state_strided_data_df_state1_only_tica['tica_2'].tolist()

tica_1_hist, tica_2_hist, z_value = imported_get_histogram(tica1_state1, tica2_state1)
free_energy_data = imported_to_free_energy(z_value)

flat_min_index = np.argmin(free_energy_data)
row_index, col_index = np.unravel_index(flat_min_index, free_energy_data.shape)

tica_1_hist_value = tica_1_hist[col_index]
tica_2_hist_value = tica_2_hist[row_index]

print(f"Index in Energy Matrix: ({row_index}, {col_index})")
print(f"Corresponding TICA 1 Value: {tica_1_hist_value}")
print(f"Corresponding TICA 2 Value: {tica_2_hist_value}")

```

This gives us as outputs the TICA-1 and TICA-2 coordinates of the points of lowest free energy for the macrostate 1, i.e., (2.03, -0.11). With the `imported_plot_free_energy` pyEMMA command we could plot the position of this point within the free energy contour plot of just macrostate 1. This command is dependent on the function `imported_get_cmap` (which is loaded in # 0.3 Definitions).

```

S1_min = [tica_1_hist_value, tica_2_hist_value]
bacins_points = [S1_min]
bacins_states = ["S1"]

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(5, 4))
imported_plot_free_energy(tica1_state1, tica2_state1, ax=ax)
ax.scatter(*zip(*bacins_points), color='red', marker='.')
for (x, y), label in zip(bacins_points, bacins_states):
    ax.text(x, y, label, color='red', fontsize=12)
ax.set_xlabel('TICA$1$')
ax.set_ylabel('TICA$2$')
fig.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

Because free energy is “normalized” by making the lowest value on the series equal to zero, the scale of Figure 14 has changed respect to 13. Now we can see a specific feature of the point that has been selected, which is that it doesn't seem to be perfectly centered. We suppose that the main reason for this behavior is a combination of the fact that this state is less visited (we saw its population is 0.19) and that it is significantly more spread than macrostate 2 on the TICA space. The latter seems reasonable as distances and angles can vary more freely when no H-bonding is present. These two features make the basin shape more susceptible to

Figure 14: Location of the point with lowest free energy within the time-lagged independent component space of macrostate 1.

Figure 15: Location of the point with lowest free energy within the time-lagged independent component space of macrostate 2.

fluctuations within the trajectories (even though they are long). The effect of this selection is more deeply discussed on the manuscript, so we continue with doing this analysis for the macrostate 2, which lead to the coordinates (-0.50 , -0.10) (Figure 15). We skip the codes and plot here, for brevity's sake, but they can be seen in the `02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb` file. We also plot these points with the free energy and density contour plots as defined in the `pyEMMA` library, to check for consistency.

2. Find the desired number of frames (here ten) nearest to each macrostate point.

Now that we have the two reference points, we need to find the 10 closest frames to each one, and get the necessary data to export the atom coordinates from the original `md.nc` files. To that end, we create the variable `complete_data_and_tica_concatenated` which is an array (a 400000 x 7 matrix) in which the following information is displayed for each frame, in order: COH angle, OHO angle, OH distance, trajectory number, frame number (within that trajectory), TICA-1 value, TICA-2 value.

```

complete_data_and_tica = []
for index, array in enumerate(data):
    tica_array = tica.transform(array) #Applying the tica transformation to the original arrays
    row_number = array.shape[0]
    ordered_data_file_number = np.full((row_number, 1), index + 1)
    frame_in_MD_trajectory = np.arange(1, row_number + 1).reshape(-1, 1)
    #Frame number is converted to start from one to the use that variable in cpptraj
    augmented_array = np.hstack((array, ordered_data_file_number, frame_in_MD_trajectory, tica_array))
    complete_data_and_tica.append(augmented_array)

complete_data_and_tica_concatenated = np.vstack(complete_data_and_tica)

```

02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb

With this table, we can use the `np.linalg.norm()` command to compute the distance of each frame (in TICA terms) to our reference points. Then, `np.argsort()` reorders the frames by distance and, by defining the “k” variable equal to 10, we can save that number of smallest distances. We use the previously defined `selected_columns` and `tica_dimension` variables to dynamically select the columns in which the numpy calculations are done.

```

first_tica_column = len(selected_columns) + 2
last_tica_column = first_tica_column + tica_dimension

start_frame_info = len(selected_columns)
end_frame_info = start_frame_info + 2

```

We will save the frame numbers in the `basin_data_indices` parameter and we will create a list of labels corresponding to each macrostate (`state_labels`). With these variables we can return to `complete_data_and_tica_concatenated` to extract the information required to go on the next step, that is determining which trajectory each of the 20 frames belong to, its frame index, which macrostate it is associated to, and also which order of appearance (from closest to farthest) corresponds to that particular frame. This information is then saved in the parameter `selected_frames`, that can be printed to inspect them.

```

k = 10 # SET ACCORDINGLY
basins_points = [S1_min, S2_min]
basin_data_indices = []
state_labels = []
order_number = []

for point in range(len(basins_points)):
    distante_to_tica_target = np.linalg.norm(complete_data_and_tica_concatenated
   [:, first_tica_column:last_tica_column] - basins_points[point], axis=1)
    indices_closest_to_tica_target = np.argsort(distante_to_tica_target)[:k]
    basin_data_indices.append(indices_closest_to_tica_target)
    state_labels.extend([basins_states[point]] * k)
    order_number.append(range(k))

basin_data_indices_flat = np.concatenate(basin_data_indices).tolist()
order_number_flat = np.concatenate(order_number).tolist()

run_indices_of_selected_frames = complete_data_and_tica_concatenated[basin_data_indices_flat,
start_frame_info:end_frame_info][:, 0].astype(int) - 1
frame_number_in_run = complete_data_and_tica_concatenated[basin_data_indices_flat,
start_frame_info:end_frame_info][:, 1].astype(int)

selected_frames = [[data_files[i], i+1, f, g, h+1] for i, f, g, h in zip(run_indices_of_selected_frames,
frame_number_in_run, state_labels, order_number_flat)]

```

3. Export the coordinates of the relevant molecules for each of the $10 \times 2 = 20$ frames.

Now we know which frames are closest to our two representative points, and to which trajectory they belong. What we need now is to dynamically generate cpptraj files to extract from the `md.nc` files the coordinates of the relevant atoms (in the main manuscript it was shown that only H-bonded solvent molecules are needed, aside the coordinates of the dye). Given the current commands of cpptraj in Amber24, we need to do this in two steps. First we export the coordinates of all the atoms on our frames of interest as a `pdb`. Then we process each `pdb` to select just the molecules we need. For the first step, we need one cpptraj file for each trajectory, while the second step requires one cpptraj script for each of the 20 frames. Thus, we begin by creating a dictionary in which the trajectory number is used as index.

```

frames_in_run = defaultdict(list)
for traj_file, run_number, frame_number, state, order_number in selected_frames:
    frames_in_run[traj_file].append([frame_number, state, run_number, order_number])

```

Now we can write the cpptraj files from the data in this dictionary. We have to take into account that cpptraj requires that the MD trajectory and topology filenames as inputs. The script assumes every trajectory is called `md.nc` and we set the topology name at the beginning of the code.

```

today_str = datetime.today().strftime('%y/%m/%d')
top_name = "BBF_EOH" #SET ACCORDINGLY

for traj, frames_list in frames_in_run.items():
    run_number = frames_list[0:1][0][2]
    filename = f"cpptraj_multiplePDBs_run_{run_number:02d}_date_{today_str}.in"
    frames_lists_ordered_by_frame = sorted(frames_list, key=lambda item: item[0])
    #This makes it easier to inspect outputs
    with open(filename, "w") as f:
        f.write(f"parm {top_name}.top\n")
        f.write(f"trajin md.nc\n")
        #CHANGE IF THE NAME OF EACH NC FILE IS DIFFERENT

        # One trajout line per frame
        for frame_detail in frames_lists_ordered_by_frame:
            frame_number = frame_detail[0]
            state_number = frame_detail[1]
            order_number = frame_detail[3]
            f.write(
                f"trajout frame_{frame_number}_run_{run_number:02d}_state_{state_number}_"
                f"order_{order_number}_date_{today_str}.pdb pdb onlyframes {frame_number}\n"
            )
        f.write("run\n")

```

We create a `03_cpptraj` subfolder and move the files produced in the preceding step into a subfolder `01_pdb`. Now we need the second set of inputs in which only the required molecules are saved, depending on the macrostate. Instead of one input for each trajectory, here we will generate one input for each frame. We start by defining the names in Amber of the photoactive species and the solvent.

```

dye_resname = "BBF"
solvent_resname = "EOH"

```

Now we generate the files for the frames corresponding to the macrostate 1, (named “S1” within this script and BBF-NHB in the manuscript). As there are no H-bond present here, we showed in the manuscript that only the BBF coordinates are needed. This can be done using the `strip` command in `cpptraj`. It is important to pay attention to the fourth line, in which we specify with which macrostate we will work.

```

for traj, frames_list in frames_in_run.items():
    for frame_detail in frames_list:
        state_number = frame_detail[1]
        if state_number == "S1": #SET ACCORDINGLY
            frame_number = frame_detail[0]
            run_number = frame_detail[2]
            order_number = frame_detail[3]
            filename = (
                f"cpptraj_frame_{frame_number}_run_{run_number:02d}_state_{state_number}_"
                f"order_{order_number}_date_{today_str}.in"
            )
            with open(filename, "w") as f:
                f.write(f"parm {top_name}.top\n")
                f.write(
                    f"trajin frame_{frame_number}_run_{run_number:02d}_state_{state_number}"
                    f"_order_{order_number}_date_{today_str}.pdb\n"
                )
                f.write(f"strip !:{dye_resname}\n")
                f.write(
                    f"trajout state-{state_number}-order-{order_number}-frame-{frame_number}"
                    f"-run-{run_number:02d}-date-{today_str}.xyz nobox\n"
                )
            f.write("run\n")

```

Now we do the same for the frames corresponding to the macrostate 2 (“S2” or BBF@EtOH). In this case, we need the coordinates of BBF and that of the closest EtOH molecule to the O1 atom of BBF. We can do that with the `closest` command in `cpptraj`. We will also need to indicate the name of the atom around which the `closest` command is run and the number of EtOH molecules (O1, in this case).

02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb

```
oxygen = "O1" #We know we only see a H-bond near BBF@O1, so this is the only atom variable we need
nmolO1 = 1 #SET ACCORDINGLY
```

02_CPPTRAJ.ipynb

```
for traj, frames_list in frames_in_run.items():
    for frame_detail in frames_list:
        state_number = frame_detail[1]
        if state_number == "S2": #SET ACCORDINGLY
            frame_number = frame_detail[0]
            run_number = frame_detail[2]
            order_number = frame_detail[3]
            near_atom = oxygen #CHANGE IF CASE NECESSARY
            filename = (
                f"cpptraj_frame_{frame_number}_run_{run_number:02d}_state_{state_number}"
                f"_order_{order_number}_date_{today_str}.in"
            )
            with open(filename, "w") as f:
                f.write(f"parm {top_name}.top\n")
                f.write(
                    f"trajin frame_{frame_number}_run_{run_number:02d}_state_{state_number}"
                    f"_order_{order_number}_date_{today_str}.pdb\n"
                )
                f.write(
                    f"closest {nmolO1} :{dye_resname}@{near_atom} solventmask :{solvent_resname} closestout"
                    f" state-{state_number}-frame-{frame_number}-run-{run_number}-{today_str}.dat nobox\n"
                )
                f.write(f"trajout state-{state_number}-order-{order_number}-frame-{frame_number}-"
                    f"run-{run_number:02d}-date-{today_str}.xyz nobox\n")
            )
            f.write("run\n")
```

We move the 20 cpptraj input files to the subfolder 03_cpptraj\02_xyz. Now we need to paste every cpptraj input file to the 4_Features folder, in which the four trajectories would be located. Once there we can initially move cpptraj inputs files to their respective subfolder ({01..04}).

Shell

```
for dir in {01..04}; do mv cpptraj*run_${dir}*.in ${dir}; done
```

Now we continue by running the cpptraj inputs that generate the pdb files.

Shell

```
for dir in {01..04}; do cd ${dir};cpptraj -i cpptraj_multiple*.in -o /dev/null & cd ..; done
```

We continue by running the cpptraj files that filter the pdb files.

Shell

```
for dir in {01..04}; do cd ${dir};cpptraj -i cpptraj_frame*.in -o /dev/null & cd ..; done
```

We are left with several *.xyz files that we move to the 8_TDDFT/04_tddft-inputs/xyz folder to continue with the next step.

4. Create and run Gaussian inputs from these 20 sets of coordinates.

Within the folder 8_TDDFT/04_tddft-inputs we run our script XYZ-TDDFT.py in order to transform each .xyz file to a Gaussian TD-DFT input. The script will ask for details to create the Gaussian input files. If we run the script by entering python3 XYZ-TDDFT.py in the command line we then need to write:

1. "continue" to start the script.
2. "3" to select Ethanol as the solvent.
3. "yes" to confirm.

4. We suggest “CAMB3LYPw02” as name of the method.
5. “cam-b3lyp” to indicate the DFT functional.
6. “6-31+G(D) to indicate the basis set.
7. “2” to indicate the use of our custom IOP.
8. “continue” to use default options for running the calculations.
9. “continue” to do not add top keywords.
10. “finish” to end the script.

A `com` subfolder with the Gaussian input files is generated. We can run these inputs using a for loop in the command line. For example, we use a custom script to initialize the gaussian calculation using slurm.

```
for input in *.com;do g16s16 ${input}; done
```

Shell

Once the calculations are done, we need to extract the data, and we can automate that step too.

5. Process the results of the 20 Gaussian outputs.

We moved the Gaussian calculation outputs in the `8_TDDFT/05_tddft-outputs/log` folder. Here we use the `TDDFT-RPS.py` script by running `python3 TDDFT-RPS.py` in the command line. No inputs are needed, but here the name conventions used on the `cpptraj` input files and on the `XYZ-TDDFT.py` script allows our script to create an excel file: `Results_TDDFT_R1.xlsx`. From here, results can be compared with that of the main manuscript, in particular the fact that we have two excitation averages to report, because we identified two macrostates during the MSM fitting.

References

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